

**SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS INFLUENCING MATERNAL HEALTH IN
ABULOMA KINGDOM OF PORT LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF RIVERS
STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

Socio-cultural factors influencing maternal health have been a global health issue faced by mothers. This study specifically aimed at investigating the extent to which socio-cultural factors influenced maternal health of women residing in Abuloma Kingdom of Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State. The population for this study comprised women of child-bearing age (15 – 49 years). Cross-sectional design was employed; a multi-stage sampling technique was used to select three hundred and sixty (360) respondents. A semi-structured and validated questionnaire with reliability coefficient of 0.77 was used for collection of data. (61.1%) 220 of the respondents had experienced some form of violence, 120 (33.3%) had experienced violence from their husbands while (36.85%) 139 received violence from their in-laws. In conclusion, this study has shown that maternal health challenges in Abuloma Kingdom will continue to be a problem if adequate attention is not provided, especially in the area of social factors that have affected maternal health and the common cultural beliefs/practices that are associated with maternal health. It is therefore recommended that, policies on gender violence should be re-enforced in the kingdom. There should be targeted health policies towards the well-being of mothers during pregnancies at work place. Policies should provide flexible working hours for pregnant women, such as closing earlier than others to avoid the pressure on the road and to be able to attend to home activities, and also for them to have enough time to prepare and rest for the next day activities.

Keywords: socio-cultural, maternal, health, women, childbearing age.